

The qb SoftHand Industry: a Collaborative Robotic Hand for the Industry

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Abstract— soft-robotics technology were recently used, in research, to design revolutionary hands that can be capable of changing forever the way automated grasping is conceived, thanks to their capability of interacting in a simple, delicate yet forceful way, with the surrounding environment, objects, and humans, while limiting the risk of hurting the operators, spoiling the products to be handled, or damaging the robot itself. This paper present qb SoftHand Industry, a new advanced anthropomorphic robotic hand based on soft-robotics technology and designed for industrial tasks, which complies to the standards and certifications of industrial and collaborative robotics and is compatible with the main robots and cobots on the market.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robot grippers are meant to replace human hands in all those operating conditions where humans are not safe or efficient to rely on. These include, e.g., repetitive cycles, handling of heavy loads and operating under hazardous environments. However, the ability of robots to grasp general objects in unstructured environments remains far behind that of humans. Nevertheless, in the recent past the introduction of the Pisa/IIT SoftHand **Error! Reference source not found.**, created after taking inspiration from the neuroscientific concept of soft synergies, showed one of the first example of anthropomorphic hand featuring, together with its 19 degrees of freedom, an extreme control simplicity, as it only uses one actuator to activate its adaptive synergy, which can be leveraged upon to revolutionize autonomous robotic grasping. This device, distributed as an open-hardware framework **Error! Reference source not found.**, let qbrobotics introduce, in the recent past, the qb SoftHand Research, a device that is being largely used for educational purposes in Universities, Research Institutes and R&D Laboratories to investigate Biomedical and Service Robotics, in more than 50 among universities and institutes.

Fig. 1. The qb SoftHand Industry: the device on the left, and two application scenarios on the right.

The main barriers that, until now, were hindering a wider diffusion of the SoftHand were constituted by the long list of certifications and rules products must comply with in order to be sold within the category of “collaborative devices”. This is not only due to the high standards and tight requirements, but also to the novelty of the topic (e.g. the ISO norms for collaborative end-effectors were first released in late 2018).

This paper presents the qb SoftHand Industry (see Fig. 1), the first Anthropomorphic Robotic Hand designed specifically for industrial applications and tasks, which is certified as “collaborative gripper”. It is entirely collaborative from a Hardware point of view, indeed the materials used, and the flexibility of the system allow the Hand to be safe and harmless in any situation of accidental impact. Moreover, the new qb SoftHand Industry offers a plug-and-play robot-hand integration, due to its ease of use and control, and can be used whenever is required to replicate the grasping movements of a human hand. The list of tasks that can be tackled by a system integrating the qb SoftHand Industry include testing, quality inspection, picking, complex handling, assembly, etc.

II. REFERENCE USE CASES

Trends in manufacturing technologies and initiatives are placing increased importance on the integration of robot technologies in manufacturing facilities. Despite years of considerable progress in improved sensing capabilities, 3D-pose estimation systems, and vision-guided robotics, a limiting factor in realizing full system automation is the challenge of grasping items in a randomized environment. A key component of an industrial robot is the robot gripper, which is an end-effector that is used for material handling. Robot grippers are meant to replace human hands because they are designed for repetitive cycles, handling heavy loads and operating under hazardous environments where human hands cannot operate. Currently, a large effort is devoted to the automation of all the operations that involve handling of goods (e.g. bin picking, raw food and grocery handling, and waste sorting – see Fig. 2) with industrial robots. However, today’s end-effectors are only suitable for very specific tasks, unable to provide satisfactory solutions to the problems above, opening up a significant market opportunity that motivated qbrobotics to realize the technological step to introduce an industry-level analogous to the SoftHand that recently became available to researchers all over the world.

Fig. 2. Example of application use-cases for the qb SoftHand Industry: bin-picking, handling of raw food and groceries and waste sorting.

Further challenges coming from the Industrial sector include the testing and quality inspection of components and parts, e.g. in the Automotive and Consumer Electronics fields. Moreover, also healthcare and cosmetic sectors can take

advantage of the features of the SoftHand for picking and handling delicate products with different shapes and consistency.

III. MAIN SPECIFICATIONS AND FEATURES

Starting from the original concept of the Pisa/IIT SoftHand, qrobotics re-designed the system from scratch according to a few important specifications. On the functional side, the main requirement is the capability of grasping a wide variety of objects and tools. So, the hand was conceived to be able to execute whole hand grasp of tools, properly and strongly enough to operate them under arm and wrist control, but it is also able to achieve fine tip grasps. The main non-functional requirements are resilience against force, overexertion and impacts, and safety in interactions with humans. Moreover, all the design process was performed in compliance with the most important list of norms and certificatory standards, as reported in TABLE I.

TABLE I. QB SOFTHAND INDUSTRY – CERTIFICATIONS & STANDARDS

Code	Topic
ISO 13849-1/-2	Performance Level
ISO/TS 15066	Collaborative Robots
ISO/TR 20218-1	Robotics -- Safety design for industrial robot systems -- Part 1: End-effectors
ISO 9409-1-50-4-M6	Manipulating industrial robots -- Mechanical interfaces -- Part 1: Plates
IEC 60529 - IP65	International Protection Rating
IEC 61000-6-1/-6-2	Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)
ISO 10210-1/-2	Hot finished structural hollow sections of non-alloy and fine grain steels

The final product, the qb SoftHand Industry, was designed with an anthropomorphic shape, 19 degrees of freedom in four fingers and an opposable thumb. The actuation system is tendon-driven and features a single motor to open and close the 5 fingers together while replicating the first synergy of the human hand movement in a flexible and adaptable grasp.

The Hand is a collaborative end-effector and thanks to its safety and ease of use and is also compatible with main cobot brands available on the market. Considering that the intended application is industry, to create a device compatible not only with cobots but also with traditional Industrial robots, we relied on an external driver allowing easy integration with all robots, be them collaborative or not. From a technical point of view, the SoftHand Industry represents the state of the art of human-like hands available on the market thanks to the performances obtained and to the unique features of the mechanics, which are resumed in TABLE II.

TABLE II. QB SOFTHAND INDUSTRY - MAIN SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Value	Unit
Power grasp payload	2	Kg
Pinch grasp payload	0.6	Kg
Hanging payload	5	Kg

Parameter	Value	Unit
Weight	0.89	Kg
Closing time	1.2	s
Wrist Angle range	0 - 90	° (deg)
Wrist Angle resolution	7.5	° (deg)

Moreover, the qb SoftHand Industry is water and dust resistance (IP65) and features the possibility of changing its glove to match special applications. Finally, it communicates natively on two of the most widespread industrial protocols: EtherCAT and UDP.

A. Compatibility and integration

Besides a flexible end-effector, a solution able to replace human operators in repetitive or hazardous environments involve several other important components. Two of the most important are a perception system and a robot able to safely interact with objects, environment and people.

Among robotic manipulators, particular interest goes toward the new generation of collaborative robots (cobots), which can safely operate in unstructured environments and in the presence of human operators, as in the case of unexpected impacts, they are designed not to be harmful for the operator.

The qb SoftHand Industry is compatible with all main robots and cobots on the market. As an example, qrobotics collaborated with Universal Robots A/S to promote the qb SoftHand Industry as the first Anthropomorphic Robotic Hand plug-and-play with the UR+ environment. UR+ is an ecosystem of hardware and software solutions compatible with UR robots that offer plug&play implementation and programming. The hand is also compatible with all versions of UR Robots including the new e-series model.

Apart from UR, the device is compatible with other important robots such as Panda by Franke Emika thanks to an APP developed to let the Hand easily run on FE system. qrobotics realized integrations also with KUKA, Yaskawa, Mitsubishi, Denso, Rethink Robotics and others. Considering the integrations realized for traditional industrial robots, we can mention a cooperation with ABB company.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The qb SoftHand Industry is a new advanced anthropomorphic robotic hand based on soft-robotics technology and designed for industrial tasks. It complies to the standards and certifications of industrial and collaborative robotics and is compatible with the main robots and cobots on the market. This opens a series of important exploitation possibilities in Industry, where of the benefits of soft robotics can revolutionize several applications.

REFERENCES

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